

ISic1662

I.Sicily inscription 1662

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Θάρσι Ἴλφ
2. ιε οὐδὶς ἄθ
3. ἀνατος Ὠρίω
4. νι ἔνταῦθα
5. κῖτε

Apparatus

Text after Agnello 1963

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645120

Bibliography

Agnello, G. 1963. Ancora sull'iscrizione messinese di Ulpio Niceforo. *Cronache di Archaeologia e di Storia dell'Arte*. 2: 79-83. At 82

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